

Global Surgery Education in Rwanda: Market and Needs Survey

Summary of Global Surgery Postgraduate Education Needs Assessment

1. Introduction

A rapid assessment was done to determine the need and relevance for Global Surgery training in Rwanda and Africa at large. The assessment was conducted through a google form sent to various professionals and experts in surgery, anesthesia, obstetrics and related fields, with 13 respondents.

2. Respondent's Engagement in Global Surgery

Majority (85.6%) were already engaged in global surgery work as defined by Byass as "an area of study, research, practice, and advocacy that seeks to improve health outcomes and achieve health equity for all people who need surgical and anaesthesia care, with a special emphasis on underserved populations and populations in crisis. It uses collaborative, cross-sectoral, and transnational approaches and is a synthesis of population-based strategies with individual surgical and anaesthesia care."

Thematic analysis of responses showed four areas of participant involvement in global surgery- clinical practice (e.g. surgery in crises populations, rural surgical care, cleft surgery), education and training (e.g. championing Non-technical skills, COSECSA surgeon training), global surgery conference attendance, global surgery advocacy(including social media advocacy), and surgical research (including injury research).

3. Need for Additional Qualifications in Global Surgery

In response to whether or not respondents had already gotten additional qualifications in global surgery or related surgical fields, the majority of respondents confirmed that they had not, while only 2 (15.4%) had a non-academic fellowship certificate in a Global Surgery related field. See **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing response to the question “Have you sought additional qualifications in Global Surgery, or any other related surgical qualification?”

Of all 13 respondents, **100% acknowledged that they would be interested in formal training in global surgery.**

This dearth of academic certification in Global Surgery in Rwanda and the region underscores the need for an academic programme to supply opportunity for knowledge and certification. The unanimous statement of interest in a Global Surgery course by all respondents reflects the market demand.

4. Barriers Identified to taking part in a UGHE Global Surgery Course and/or Continuing Professional Development.

We attempted to identify hindrances to taking part in a global surgery programme with UGHE, and 14.3% of responses identified no barriers that would limit health professionals currently involved in Global Surgery from taking UGHE Global Surgery courses. Barriers identified by other respondents included inability to take time off employment (7.1%), barriers of financial cost (28.6%), the use of a strictly in-person modality (14.3%), distance barriers (14.3%), presence of reliable internet (7.1%), and time requirements (14.3%).

5. Global Surgery Programming

When asked about the top three to five key skills or knowledge respondents would like to gain from such a global surgery program, the top responses were in knowledge areas of Global Surgery research methods, surgical leadership and management, Global Surgery advocacy, Global Surgery specific grant writing, basics of Global Surgery, National Surgical Obstetrics and Anesthesia Plans and policy development. **Table 1** shows the skill and knowledge areas requested by study participants with the number of suggesting participants.

Table 1: Course Content- Areas of Course Knowledge or Skill Suggested by Respondents for the Curriculum

S/N	Global Surgery Knowledge or Skill Area Respondents Would Want to Gain from a UGHE Program	Number of Suggesting Respondents *
1	Global Surgery Research Methodology	8
2	Surgical Leadership and Management Skills,	4
3	Global Surgery Advocacy	4
4	Global Surgery Grant Proposal Writing	3
5	Understanding Global Health in relation to Global Surgery	3
6	National Surgery Obstetrics and Anesthesia Plans and policy development	2
7	Concept of Surgical Access for LMICs	2
8	Global Surgery Education	2
9	The Trauma pandemic, evidence-based containment interventions, and trauma management with an LIC focus	2
10	Burden of Disease- Current global surgery interventions	1
11	Optimizing operating theatre use	1

12	Global Surgery Quality Improvement	1
13	Surgical Safety,	1
14	Global Surgery Financing	1
15	Laparoscopic surgery skill	1
16	Endoscopy skill	1
17	Laparoscopic surgery skill	1

*Each respondent suggested more than one area of knowledge and skill. This column suggests popular weighting for the knowledge/skill areas

6. Global Surgery Course Modality and Course Delivery Options

Continuing professional development in Global Surgery can be offered as a dedicated Masters’ degree (e.g. 1-2 years full-time, course-based or thesis-based), a diploma (e.g. 1 year, part-time, no thesis), or certificate (e.g. days to weeks). The main differences are that a Masters degree takes the longest to complete, while certificate programs are shortest and will only comprise one module or one topic. Based on this information, we asked what qualification respondents would prefer in a Global Surgery program, and why they had that preference.

Masters degree was preferred by the majority of respondents (n=8, 61.5%), while the certificate course was preferred by about 30.8%. One person stated no preferences. No respondents particularly requested the Diploma, and 1 person responded that any of the modes would be good as long as Global Surgery principles are learned.

The theme that emerged for why the Master's degree was preferred was the need for more in depth and complete knowledge and understanding.

Respondent 2: *“Master’s level as this will allow more in depth understanding of quality/research processes that inhance better surgical outcomes”*

Respondent 7: *“Dedicated master degree because i need a complete and full level of knowledge”*

Certificate courses were preferred by few others to allow for selection of courses of interest, and because of the possible full-time nature of a Master’s degree. The theme of

preference for the Master's degree over certificate courses, if the Master's was delivered in a blended format also came up in responses.

Respondent 1: *"I would choose Certificate. I cant be away from my work place full time. If any change the Masters can be given in mixed physical and virtual programs, I would prefer that."*

Respondent 9: *"Being a holder of a Master qualification, an additional master degree wouldn't add much to my qualifications. I would therefore prefer a Certificate Course as it allows me to select topics of interest and value to me."*

In terms of course delivery, most participants (n=9, 69.2%) preferred blended learning with in-person and online components while (n=4, 30.8%) preferred courses completely online. See **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Response to the question, "Would you prefer to do a Global Surgery course in person or in an online or blended format?"

7. Funding, Fees and Course Payments

Majority (n=9, 69.2%) would pay or consider paying for continuing professional development in Global Surgery (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Would you consider paying for a continuing professional development in Global Surgery?

8. Motivations and Application of Skill Gained

Analysis of survey participants' motivations to do the Global Surgery Master's or Certificate Courses showed that the majority were driven by the need for implementation science and application of skill gained in day-to-day practice. Potential students wanted skills to do research, advocacy, create policy change, improve access to surgical care, and better serve underserved populations. Very specific motivators like the need to establish a strong Global Surgery Centre in departments of Surgery, positioning for job opportunities, and meeting the need for continuing professional development were also motivators. This implies that participants know that this course will be relevant to their development in professional and practice environments, and essential to improving surgical equity in the country, region and beyond.

9. Potential for Career Advancement

In response to the prompt "If you completed a Global Surgery qualification, how might that further advance your career?", a number of potential areas following global surgery higher education were obtained.

1. Advancement to Policy Making Positions

Respondent 1: “I could join policy makers and bring the skills and knowledge I get from the training to the policy level.”

2. Advancement to Leadership and Administration Positions in Surgery

Respondent 3: “A qualification in global surgery will help me become: 1. A leader in surgical and anesthesia care delivery 2. A surgical scholar 3. An international figure in surgery”

3. Advancement in Research Positions

4. Academic Advancement

Respondent 4: *“It will help me broaden my horizon in non-clinical aspect of surgery. It will also advance my career in sub-specialty, academic promotion...”*

5. Improved Networks and Advancement in Professional Relationships

Respondent 4: *“...it will create opportunities to meet giants in surgery”*

Respondent 6: *“BE open to the world...and participate in surgical access equity”*

6. Continuing Medical Education

Respondent 5: *“Gaining CPD points for relicensing to practice”*

7. The satisfaction of participating in improved surgical care

Respondent 9: *“In the practice of surgery in the third world countries, research and development of a better healthcare system. Development of innovative practice and/or technologies for improved health care”*

Assessment Conclusions

This needs assessment clearly outlines the gap in Global Surgery higher education in the region. Up to 84.6% do not have any certification in Global Surgery, and no respondents have a Master's degree in Global Surgery, despite a high level of engagement in widespread aspects of global surgery work (85.6%). All respondents (100%) are interested in advanced training in Global Surgery, and most support a Master's degree programme (61.5%) and a few alternative short course certifications (30.8%). Top weighted programme content suggested by respondents included Global Surgery research methodology, leadership and management, advocacy, and policy training among others. Most wanted a Masters degree program (61.5%), or certificate courses (30.8%), with no significant interest in a diploma (non Master's) program. Support was greatest for a blended learning modality (69.2%) with in-person and online components. Most (69.2%) would pay or consider paying to attend the program, however, the major potential barrier to participation in this educational program by respondents would be barriers of financial cost (28.6%). Motivations for the course were primarily to implement change in their local, regional, and global practice environment, and the program shows immense potential to provide job opportunities, professional and personal advancement to participants.